

Review

Gametes cryopreservation and restoration among cancer patients: A clinical approach

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Abstract— With the following advancement in medical research and increased therapeutic options, survival rates in cancer patients have increased significantly. Meanwhile, there are few side effects associated with these cancer treatments which lead to infertility. The available standard option for fertility preservation and restoration in such patients is gametes cryopreservation before taking any cancer-curing treatment. Physicians should discuss possible fertility loss and available potential strategies for its preservation with all patients of reproductive age. This article reviews the need for cryopreservation of human gametes before cancer-treating therapies, challenges to be overcome during the procedure, and methods of preserving the gametes with the final aim of improvement of oncofertility counseling in the future.

Keywords— oncofertility, fertility after cancer treatment, cryopreservation of gametes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fertility preservation offers the potential strategies to the people who want to postpone their parenthood, oncologic patients, or other individuals which undergo such treatments which can affect their fertility after the treatment[1].

When during cancer treatment body is exposed to some radiations or chemicals; these may cause gonadotoxicity (i.e. damage to gonads) which can adversely affect the fertility of patients. So, during oncofertility counseling patients are made aware of the possible options to preserve their fertility and the success possibility of live birth after opting for any of those strategies[2]–[4]. Most of the patients agree to preserve their fertility before treatment. However, many patients deny undergoing preservation procedures. It can be defined by the fact that they do not want to procrastinate their treatment, or they are unaware of post-treatment fertility loss[5]–[7]. Gamete preservation is preferred when patients refuse to preserve embryo. These strategies also avoid the negative effects on patients' lifelike lower marriage rates, and their post-surgery health. Before preserving the gametes, proper controlled stimulation is done to induce multiple gametic cells to increase the success rate per cell[8], [9]. As stimulation requires a time of at least weeks, it is considered

safe only in the cases when treatment can be postponed for that much time. Safety measures are also taken in patients with hormone-sensitive cancers.

However, despite the involvement of major oncology and reproductive medicine associations, fertility preservation has been adopted by very few people. This may be explained by the unawareness of the topic among doctors and patients.

A. The negative effect of chemotherapy on gametes

Chemotherapy adversely affects fertility. In males, sperm output reduces due to the side effects of therapy and therapeutic drugs. These agents damage the spermatogenic epithelium. If, however, the epithelium survives, there are other potential dangers too, as the radiations and chemicals are mutagenic which can either cause damage to the DNA or can modify its gene expression[10], [11].

In females, the exact mechanism of gonadotoxicity is not known. Generally, stroma and granulosa cells are more affected but direct toxicity on oocytes by anticancer drugs is also seen.

Anticancer drugs like Cyclophosphamide (the most widely used agent in cancer treatments) generate double-stranded nicks in DNA which interrupts the ovarian function and induces infertility. Mitomycin C causes cross-linking in ovarian DNA[12], [13].

Anthracyclines Doxorubicin inhibits the Topoisomerase II. This agent may either damage ovaries directly or can cause injuries to granulosa cells which finally leads apoptosis of cell cycle arrest[14], [15].

B. Challenges during the procedure of cryopreservation

During cryopreservation, technicians face major problems during the preservation of oocytes because oocytes are the largest cells in the human body, but they have a very low surface area to volume ratio. Consequently, oocytes retain water during preservation which may cause intracellular injuries due to ice formation.

Moreover, osmotic stress can be generated due to different concentrations of cryopreservative agents. Cryopreservation can also thicken the zona pellucid. Some studies have shown that cryopreservation can alter the expression of genes that are related to apoptosis, cell cycle, and oxidative stress[16].

Formation of ice crystals inside the sperm cell can also cause intracellular damage but sperms are less likely to get damaged because of low water content and high fluidity. It is seen that chilling damage can alter the structure and integrity of the plasma membrane[16]–[18].

C. Triggering the oocytes before retrieval

In females, gametes are required to be triggered by controlled ovarian stimulation (COS) to increase the yield of mature oocytes. Studies have reported that when GnRH - agonist ovulatory trigger to improve the safety of COS by decreasing the frequency of ovarian hyperstimulation condition (OHSS). Furthermore, rising information additionally recommends that the use of the GnRH agonist trigger expands the yield of developing oocytes when contrasted and the use of a standard hCG[19].

D. Collection of gametes

Semen is collected from the patients according to the guidelines of WHO and protocols obtained from different studies to preserve the sperms using standard strategies.

Oocytes from female patients are obtained by general laparoscopic retrieval of ovarian tissue using general anesthesia. Oophorectomy is performed based on the decision taken by the IVF units surgeon and the medical staff. Their decision differs depending on the size of the ovary and the type of cancer treatment. The average operative time is 40 minutes. The use of any dissection device that can lead to collateral electric or thermal injury to the ovarian tissue is avoided. After collection, gametes are sent to the IVF unit for cryopreservation[20].

II. DIFFERENT METHODS OF CRYOPRESERVATION OF GAMETES

Slow freezing and vitrification are the available methods for oocytes cryopreservation. In the former method, oocytes are chilled to below freezing point along with cryoprotectant agents like sugars and propanediol to overcome crystallization and the damage caused by the osmotic stress. Vitrification means "glass formation" i.e. freezing a liquid into a solid with the formation of crystals. In this process, oocytes are immersed in highly concentrated cryoprotectants for the long term[21].

In the cases of sperm cryopreservation, glycerol is the most common cryoprotective agent. Treating semen with heparin-binding proteins before cryopreservation has shown fewer injuries due to freezing in many studies. Methods used for cryopreservation are the same as that of oocyte cryopreservation.

Accuracy of cryopreservation depends highly on the operator, vitrification in particular because it requires to be completed within seconds[22], [23].

III. RESTORATION OF FERTILITY IN CANCER PATIENTS AFTER TREATMENT

A. Thawing

Freeze cells are removed from liquid nitrogen storage and quickly kept in a water bath at a temperature of 37 degrees Celsius. Then the warmed cells are transferred into a tube and 9 ml PBS of cGMP kept at 4 degrees Celsius for 1:10 dilution. Cells are centrifuged and again Pbs is added. After the thawing of cells, these are sent to the laboratory for sterility testing[24], [25].

Then the most active cells are chosen to perform IVF followed by embryo implantation in the mother's womb.

B. Efficacy of cryopreservation technique

During the initial years of use, the success of cryopreservation was low but slowly many live births were reported by using cryopreserved gametes. In 2013, ASRM approved cryopreservation use for cancer patients by removing the tag of 'experimental'.

Table 1: Comparative analysis of semen parameters before banking and after thawing[26].

	Pre-storage	Post-thawing	p value
Number of spermatozoa (million/ml)	27 ± 28.41	10.66 ± 14.37	**
Motility a + b (%)	33.16 ± 20.08	3.16 ± 7.11	**
Total motility count (million/ml)	12.08 ± 21.24	2.83 ± 5.46	**
Vitality (%)	60.28 ± 17.7	35.74 ± 22.86	**

Semen parameters: number of spermatozoa (million/ml), motility a + b (%), total motility count (million/ml) and vitality (%) before banking and after thawing. Statistical analysis was performed with Student's t test and data were considered significant for **p < 0.001.

Table 2: Reproductive outcome of 19 patients stratified by cancer type[26].

	Tumor of testis (n = 8)	Lymphoma (n = 6)	Other (n = 5)	p
Female age (years)	34.75 ± 5.33	35.5 ± 5.35	35.6 ± 3.83	NS
Male age (years)	32.5 ± 6.24	36.5 ± 10.21	34.4 ± 4.03	NS
Duration of storage (years)	3.35 ± 3.24	4.5 ± 3.99	2.6 ± 1.5	NS
Number of oocytes inseminated (n)	6 ± 3.43	4 ± 1.41	4.2 ± 1.94	NS
Number of oocytes fertilized (n)	2.13 ± 2.37	2 ± 1.15	3 ± 2.1	NS
Number of oocytes cleaved (n)	2 ± 2.35	2 ± 1.15	3 ± 2.1	NS
Transferred embryos (n)	1.25 ± 0.66	1.83 ± 1.34	2.2 ± 1.72	NS
Fertilization rate	35.42%	50%	71.43%	NS
Cleavage rate	94.11%	100%	100%	NS
Implantation rate	40%	27.27%	0	NS
Pregnancy rate	37.5%	33.33%	0	NS

Reproductive outcomes of 19 patients who used their banked samples for 20 assisted reproductive cycles, with controlled ovarian hyperstimulations and *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) with or without intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI). Statistical analysis was performed with Student's t test and data were considered significant for **p < 0.001.

IV. COUNSELING IN DIFFICULT CASES

In pre-pubertal males, counseling is a bit difficult because of their unawareness about future infertility and the lack of knowledge in that particular case.

But in females along with prepubertal girls, counseling is equally difficult in the case of old females who are at the age of above 40 as in this age group fertility treatment has a very low probability of success. In these cases, proper oncofertility counseling is required by specialists. A proper discussion is required to be made with patients about the risks, benefits, and success rates, and also the alternatives should also be discussed like egg donation or adoption.

In some cases when treatment can't be delayed, it becomes difficult to preserve fertility in females because oocyte preservation requires triggering time before the retrieval of oocytes.

Children and teenagers are also hard to counsel. COS can't be conducted in the pre-pubertal girls as they do not ovulate, so their ovarian tissue is preserved and kept for In vitro maturation (IVM).

Young female candidates may find it emotionally uncomfortable to consecutive transvaginal ultrasounds. So these patients should be counseled meticulously[24].

V. SIGNIFICANCE OF CRYOPRESERVATION OF GAMETES

By cryopreservation, gametes can be stored for a remarkably long time for restoration of fertility. Sperms can be stored for 24 years and oocytes can be stored for 30 years. So, it provides ample time for patients to get their disease cured and to recover from the weakness and then to go for parenthood.

VI. LIMITATIONS

The major drawback of cryopreservation is the lower success rates as compared to fertilization with fresh gametes. The second major limitation of this is that during thawing many cells are not able to withstand sudden heat shock and become inactive. Apart from this, there is a risk of Ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome during the triggering of ovaries[27], [28].

VII. CONCLUSION

There are potential risks of losing fertility are associated with chemotherapies and anti-cancer drugs. There are many standard strategies are available for the patients to preserve their fertility. They can preserve their gametes by the method of cryopreservation and once the disease gets cured and patients recover fully, they can go for restoration of their fertility by IVF.

Physicians should make every patient aware of these procedures and counsel them properly and should discuss every aspect related to these strategies.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to our mentors, Last but not least, we would like to thank our family for support.

Author contributions: AR suggested the topic, concept, design, and writing the first-hand manuscript. DPS and SD did an extensive literature search and the final evaluation. DPS and AR provided the technical guide. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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